

A Narrative Evaluation of Homeopathic Relevance in Treating Autoimmune Diseases, Including Rheumatoid Arthritis, with Rubrics and Justifications

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Abstract:-

➤ *Background:*

This review discusses about Autoimmune diseases exist on a physical level; they can also exist on a mental level. Understanding autoimmunity at the mental level will make homeopathic treatment easier. importance of anti-miasmatic treatment with rubrics and their justifications of Homoeopathic medicine for autoimmune diseases, rheumatoid arthritis. the repertory is an essential part of the treatment for autoimmune disorders. since it has a wide range of rubrics, including clinical rubrics that can be applied as an initial point for selecting similimum in autoimmune disorders.

➤ *Objectives:*

To review the effectiveness of Homoeopathic medicine against autoimmune diseases, and rheumatoid arthritis.

➤ *Methods:*

Google Scholar and PubMed databases were searched for these studies that analyzed the effects of Homoeopathic medicine against rheumatoid arthritis. After scrutiny of abstracts, full texts of shortlisted studies were reviewed for study design.

➤ *Results:*

The Google Scholar and PubMed databases searched for the concerned studies with the following search parameters: article types – immunity in homeopathy, statistics, control and prevention, Homoeopathic prophylaxis, and Adverse drug effects of corticosteroids. Full texts of shortlisted studies after scrutiny of abstracts were analyzed for study design, The majority of the studies show the consequences of Homoeopathic medicines used to treat the patient who tends to the condition as well as to control the ongoing inflammatory process without having any negative side effects on other body parts, thereby lowering the risk of developing further complications from the illness. and results were analyzed.

➤ *Conclusion:*

Women are more likely to suffer autoimmune disorders than men are, according to conventional sciences, yet the homeopathic concept claims that as it is autoimmune at the physical level, autoimmunity at the mental level may come before it. To put it another way, in terms of self-destruction, self-blame, by herself/himself, suicidal ideas, delusions, and destructiveness. If autoimmune at the level of the mind is understood, an effort is made here to clarify mental rubrics connected to autoimmunity by making use of synthetic repertory homeopathic therapy can be made easier.

Keywords:- Homoeopathy, Autoimmune Disorders, Immunity in Homoeopathy, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Adverse Effects.

Keymessages:- A Narrative Review on Homeopathic Intervention, as an Anti-Miasmatic Treatment for Autoimmune Illnesses in Treating Rheumatoid Arthritis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autoimmune disorders, such as thyroid, liver, and rheumatoid arthritis, are more common in women than men. The cause remains unclear. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) affects multiple systems and is linked to HLA-DR4. Factors like synovial hyperplasia and lymphocytic infiltration contribute to its progression. 0.5-1.0% of the population has RA, with women being three times more affected. ⁽¹⁾

In the last few years, doctors have begun to administer hardly any painkillers and very little steroid medication. The term Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) refers to a group of drugs that includes Methotrexate, Leflunomide, Hydroxychloroquine, and Sulphasalazine. Additionally, JAK inhibitors are commonly utilized in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. These are among the medicines recommended. Due to the aggressiveness of the disease, DMARDs are prescribed to patients 80% of the time, while biological medications or JAK inhibitors may be prescribed to 20% of patients. ⁽²⁾

According to the World Health Organization, homoeopathy is one of the second most widely accepted medical systems. ⁽³⁾ Homoeopathy treats the whole person by individualizing treatment plans and choosing constitutional medicines, which prevents the recurrence of auto-immune diseases like rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis, and others without causing additional suffering or side effects. Homoeopathy adheres to the law *similia similibus curenter*.

II. INCIDENCE, PREVALENCE, AND STATISTICS IN THE OCCURRENCE OF RA

Rheumatoid arthritis affects over 1.3 crore population in India; it is a disease that does not just affect the elderly. Most sufferers of rheumatoid arthritis are in their 20s to 40s, which is the younger age range. Among women, it is also more prevalent. Approximately 1% of people in India are affected by rheumatoid arthritis. Therefore, according to estimations, this type of arthritis affects about 10 lakh people. ⁽²⁾

Between 2013 and 2015, 22.7% of Americans (58.5 million) had arthritis, gout, lupus, fibromyalgia, or rheumatoid arthritis diagnoses by a medical professional. ⁽⁴⁾

Picture No1 Mechanism of Pathology⁽⁵⁾

Rheumatoid arthritis is a condition where joints become inflamed, and the cartilage within them degrades. This happens due to the activation of complement by IgM immune complexes that release cytokines such as TNF and IL-1. These cytokines are chemotactic for neutrophils, which are inflammatory cells that secrete lysosomal enzymes. That causes cartilaginous degradation, bone erosions, and joint deformity, as well as vasodilation and discomfort. HLA-DR4 has been linked to the disease; genetic and environmental variables may both contribute to disease onset. ⁽⁵⁾

➤ Age of Onset

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) typically manifests between the ages of 30 to 60, whereas it can affect anyone regardless of age. Young-onset rheumatoid arthritis (YORA) specifically affects individuals between 16 to 40 years old, Later-onset rheumatoid arthritis (LORA) occurs when symptoms develop after age 60. ⁽⁶⁾

➤ Risk Factors

Rheumatoid arthritis can develop for a variety of reasons. These are as follows:

If a close family member has RA, you are at a higher risk of developing it too.

Women and individuals assigned female at birth have a two to three times higher risk of developing rheumatoid arthritis. Smoking increases the risk and severity of symptoms. Obesity also increases the risk. ⁽⁷⁾

➤ The RA Disease Cycle

- Stage 1: The tissue surrounding your joint(s) is swollen in the early stages of rheumatoid arthritis. There could be some stiffness and soreness.
- In stage 2 of this condition, the inflammation starts damaging the cartilage in your joints. At this stage, you may experience stiffness and limited range of motion.
- In stage 3, inflammation causes your bones to deteriorate, leading to even more soreness, stiffness, and decreased range of motion. Physical changes may also become noticeable. As the swelling subsides
- Stage 4, joint deterioration continues, resulting in excruciating pain, edema, stiffness, and limited movement. ⁽⁸⁾

➤ *The symptoms of RA*

Symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis include pain, swelling, tenderness, and stiffness in multiple joints. Stiffness is particularly noticeable in the mornings or after prolonged periods of sitting. Pain and stiffness are felt in the same joints on both sides of the body. Other symptoms include severe exhaustion, weakness, and fever.

Physical Examination includes Inspection of your joints. Observing how you move, bend, and perform daily chores. Examine your skin for a rash or nodules. Listen to your chest for symptoms of pulmonary inflammation.

➤ *Laboratory Tests*

Rheumatoid The RF antibody test detects rheumatoid arthritis in blood, but not all patients will test positive. It can help clinicians identify the condition alongside other tests and assessments. Element (RF).

➤ *Anti-CCP (Cyclic Citrullinated Peptide) Antibodies*

Blood test detects anti-CCP in rheumatoid arthritis patients, aiding early diagnosis and confirming diagnosis using RF and RA results.

- *Complete Blood Count.*

This blood test evaluates distinct blood cell counts and can aid in the diagnosis of a, which is frequent in persons with RA.

- *Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (Also Known as the Set Rate).*

This test monitors disease activity and how well medications are functioning by evaluating inflammation in the body.

- *Protein C-Reactive.*

An inflammatory test aids in the diagnosis and progression of rheumatoid arthritis. Additional blood tests to examine general health, renal, liver, thyroid functions, muscle markers, and infection markers may be conducted.⁽⁹⁾

➤ *Allopathic Management*⁽¹⁰⁾

Fig 1 Allopathic Management

➤ *Adverse Drug Effects*

Every medicine has the potential to have side effects, thus whenever medication is administered, the therapeutic advantages must be considered along with the potential risks to choose whether to use the medication in question or not for a certain patient. Consider the possibility of bone marrow depression when treating cancer, or the possibility of slight drowsiness brought on by an antihistamine when treating the ordinary cold. ⁽¹⁰⁾

➤ *Adverse Side Effects of RA Treatment*

Aspirin, ibuprofen, or naproxen are a few examples of over-the-counter medications that some people use to manage their symptoms. These medications are referred to as NSAIDs or nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. They might also interfere with some prescription medications.

➤ *Methotrexate*

Early RA treatment is preferred to prevent excessive joint damage from inflammation. Some potential side effects of methotrexate include nausea, vomiting, altered liver function, redness, diarrhea, and mouth sores.

➤ *Leflunomide*

Leflunomide, when used alongside methotrexate, can help control RA progression, but liver damage and birth defects should be monitored through routine blood tests.

➤ *Hydroxychloroquine and Sulfasalazine*

The medicine may work better if taken with food. Skin changes are less frequent. Very rarely, the medication may have an impact on vision.

➤ *Biologics: Anti-TNF Drugs*

The therapy of RA has been significantly enhanced by biologics. They function by preventing the immune system's various parts from doing their jobs. One of the most dangerous side effects of these medications is infection because they depress the immune system.

➤ *Immunosuppressants*

Immunosuppressants, such as cyclosporine and azathioprine, were initially prescribed to prevent organ transplant rejection in RA. However, they are now infrequently used, due to potential side effects like renal damage, high blood pressure, and gout. Cytoxan, a strong immunosuppressant, is used only for severe RA and can cause low blood counts and bladder inflammation.

➤ *Older Medications: Minocycline and Gold Formulations*

Gold preparations can be effective, but may cause side effects like skin rashes, oral sores, and taste changes. Minocycline, a dated antibiotic, can treat mild RA cases.

➤ *Biologics: JAK Inhibitors*

Tofacitinib is the first biological RA therapy, and patients should report infection signs and be cautious of histoplasmosis, a common lung infection in the central and eastern US. ⁽¹¹⁾

➤ *Homeopathic Management*

According to the World Health Organization, homeopathy is the second most generally acknowledged and practiced system of medicine in the world and is developing at the fastest rate. ⁽³⁾ Homeopathy treats the person as a whole. In the case of an autoimmune disorder, rheumatoid arthritis, homeopathic medicine is used to treat the patient who tends to the condition as well as to control the ongoing inflammatory process without having any negative side effects on other body parts, thereby lowering the risk of developing further complications from the illness. ⁽¹²⁾

➤ *Anti-Miasmatic Treatment*

Anti-miasmatic drugs can treat autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, diabetes, psoriasis, and others.

Miasm is an invisible, animated creature influencing or infecting specific illness forms, involving dynamic concepts.

III. HAHNEMANN'S DYNAMIC PATHOLOGY OF DISEASE

Homeopathic theory suggests life is explained by an autocratic spiritual vital force in every living organism. Aphorism 11 of the Organon suggests sickness manifests when the vital force is disturbed by a harmful agent, which may be due to their specific dynamic influence.

➤ *Why Is Understanding Miasm Important?*

To evaluate the homeopathic prognosis, consider the symptom clarity resulting from removing layers of suppression, leading to a significant improvement in overall well-being. Anti-miasmatic medications dissolve these layers, resulting in improved feelings of well-being, increased vitality, greater appetite, restorative sleep, temperament harmony, weight growth, and clarity of present-day symptoms. These medications help eradicate suppressed symptoms, enhancing the constitution and future.

➤ *Past*

Anti-miasmatic medications' centrifugal activity helps frame the right totality by bringing suppressed symptoms to the surface, organizing symptoms, and providing a clear picture.

➤ *Present*

Miasmatic treatment involves removing suppression layers, adjusting treatment plans based on surface miasm and symptom totality, reducing illness susceptibility, and achieving long-term health restoration.

➤ *Future*

Miasmatic stigma removal improves immunity, strengthens the constitution, and prevents disease susceptibility through correct diagnosis and therapeutic purposes. ⁽¹³⁾

Picture No 2 Stages of Osteoarthritis⁽²⁸⁾

Table 1 Modalities ⁽¹³⁾

Psoric Extremities	Sychotic Extremities	Syphilitic Extremities
Various forms of rheumatism, particularly those with an inflammatory and functional basis.	The majority of mild and large joint pains are sychotic.	Sphyilis exhibits a highly erratic pattern of symptom progression.
The psora's extremities pains are typical of the neuralgic variety.	Joint deposits, tophi, and arthritic deformations. Sycosis doesn't always show symptoms and sometimes does so covertly.	Syphilitic pain is felt in lengthy bones.
	Sycotic pale, oedematous, and puffy pains include stitching, pulsating, and wandering pains. These traits include stiffness, discomfort, and lameness. Gouty arthritis is sycotic in nature.	Pains that are burning, exploding, or tearing are syphilitic. The bones don't get enough nutrients.

Table 2 Modalities of Various Miasams ⁽¹³⁾

Psora	Sycosis	Syphilis
Motion makes acute inflammatory rheumatic pain worse whereas calm, warmth, and rest make it better. When the weather gets cold, people want both internal and outward warmth. aggravated by the cold and from standing between sunrise and sunset.	aggravating rest, a wet, rainy, humid environment, thunderstorms, weather fluctuations, and meat. A barometer, the schizophrenic patient experiences pain and suffering when it rains..	Acute rheumatic pain, ulcerous inflammations, necrotic changes in the bones, and searing pains are all made worse by the beach, thunderstorms, perspiration through natural discharge, and sunset to sunrise.

➤ *Patients on Long-Term Allopathic Medication [Patients on Allopathic Medication]*

Long-term use of potent allopathic drugs, such as Cortisone tablets, prolonged antibiotic therapy, and psychotropic medications, presents significant challenges for homoeopathic treatment. Allopathic drugs can be categorized into essential, comfort, and socially essential groups. Proper treatment can improve general energy, but some medications may be lowered. Taking more potent allopathic medication can shorten the response duration of a homoeopathic remedy.

• *Cortisone –*

The main disorders for which cortisone is prescribed include allergies, rheumatoid arthritis, asthma, and autoimmune diseases. Cortisone is the drug that suppresses the immune system the most. Most homoeopathic symptoms are covered up by cortisone.

• *Antibiotics:*

Only in extreme circumstances can antibiotics be administered. Homoeopathic medicines work more quickly than antibiotics. ⁽¹⁴⁾

IV. IMMUNITY AND HOMEOPATHY

Immunity, derived from the Latin word immunize, is the body's natural defense against infections. Homoeopathy, a medical approach, aims to boost the immune system by combining drug formulations with the body's immune system. This approach considers a patient's physical, mental, and inherited circumstances, resulting in healthier patients and reduced illness. Homoeopathic medicines accelerate the body's natural healing process by administering carefully analyzed medications in small doses. Despite the unknown nature of how homoeopathic medications work, they are believed to enhance the body's defenses against infections. ⁽¹⁵⁾

➤ *Homoeopathic Studies Related to Rheumatoid Arthritis:*

Raza SA, et al, since 1790, over 3000 homoeopathic remedies have been used successfully, Rheumatic disease, affecting joints, ligaments, tendons, bones, and muscles, cannot be cured by current medical practices. Patients often seek alternative therapies, such as homoeopathy, which treats conditions like uterine fibroids and kidney stones without side effects. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Spana G, et al., 2020, The study compares the effectiveness of physiotherapy, homoeopathic medications, and a placebo in treating rheumatoid arthritis. It examines the relationship between miasms and pain management in both therapy groups. 60 patients were divided into two groups: Group A, which received homoeopathic medicine, and Group B, which received a placebo. After three months, the NPRS Scores in both groups were reduced. The study found that sycoticmiasm and Psora-sycosis showed notable improvement in Group A, while Group B's primary miasms showed only slight improvement. The most commonly given medications were Bryonia, Rhustox, and Calcareaephos. Homoeopathic treatments were found to be more effective than placebo in reducing pain in RA cases. ⁽¹⁷⁾

Priyanka D, et al, this pilot study evaluates the effectiveness of homoeopathic treatments for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in India, a prevalent autoimmune disease. Results show individual homoeopathic treatment is statistically more effective than conventional medicine, with customized remedies potentially beneficial. The study highlights the need for further research and further investigation into this condition. ⁽¹⁸⁾

V. THE METHODS

The following search criteria were used to find the relevant studies in the Google Scholar and PubMed databases: The search term used was ‘Homeopathy AND rheumatoid arthritis with search details (‘homeopathy’ [All Fields] OR ‘homeopathy’ (MeSH Terms) OR ‘homeopathy’ [All Fields] AND (‘Anti-Miasmatic’ [MeSH Terms] OR miasm [All Fields])article types – immunity in homoeopathy, statistics, control and prevention, Homoeopathic prophylaxis, Adverse drug effects of corticosteroids. Full texts of shortlisted studies after scrutiny of abstracts were analyzed for study design, The majority of the studies show the consequences of Homoeopathic medicines used to treat the patient who tends to the condition as well as to control the ongoing inflammatory process without having any negative side effects on other body parts, thereby lowering the risk of developing further complications from the illness. and results were analyzed.

VI. RESULT

Table 3 Studies Conducted to Explore the Usefulness of Homoeopathic in Rheumatoid Arthritis

Studies Conducted to Explore the Usefulness of Homoeopathic In Rheumatoid Arthritis				
S. No	Author	year	Article title	Result
	Raza SA, et al	2020	Raza SA, Ali S, Qureshi MZ, Raza A, Waqar A, Yasmeen F, Hassan HA, Naz S. Use of Homeopathic Therapeutic Regimens for the Treatment of Uterine Fibroids, Expulsion of Kidney Stones & Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Systematic Review.	Rheumatic disease, causing inflammation in joints, ligaments, tendons, bones, and muscles, cannot be cured by current medical practices, leading most patients to seek alternative therapies like homoeopathy. ⁽¹⁶⁾
	Sapna G, et al	2020	Sapna G, Sulemani AA, Ghosh S, Kansal S, Kaur P, Mehrotra S. The Relation of Miasms in Homoeopathic Treatment, as add on, in Management of Rheumatoid Arthritis. Advancements in Homeopathic Research. 2020 Nov 22;5(3):13-8.	The study compares physiotherapy, homoeopathic medications, and a placebo in treating rheumatoid arthritis. Results show that sycotic miasm improves in 7 cases with a decrease in average NPRS, while primary miasms in Group B show a slight improvement in one case. ⁽¹⁷⁾
	Priyanka D,et al	2020	Priyanka D, Mishra K, Singh J. Can individualized homoeopathic medicines bring a ray of hope to the patients of rheumatoid arthritis: A pilot study.	Rheumatoid arthritis, a prevalent autoimmune disease, can be effectively treated with customized homeopathic remedies, according to clinical case reports, observational studies, and RCTs. ⁽¹⁸⁾
	Ling HW.	2020	Ling HW. Constitutional homeopathy of five elements based on traditional Chinese medicine. Acta Scientific Medical Sciences. 2020;4(7):57-69.	Homeopathy is a treatment method that focuses on treating the cause rather than just the symptoms of a disease. It analyses symptoms and creates specific therapies for major organs using the principle of Five Elements in traditional Chinese medicine., putting more emphasis on the cause than the symptoms. ⁽¹⁹⁾
	Ling HW	2021	Ling HW. What Do All Autoimmune Diseases Have in Com? on. J Clin Exp Immunol, 6 (3): 301. 2021;304.	The author identifies patients as immunosuppressed and non-immunocompetent due to a lack of energy in internal organs. To improve immunity, she uses highly diluted

				medications like homeopathic, based on Traditional Chinese Medicine theory, by Arndt Shultz's Law as concentrated drugs reduce vital energy and can be fatal. ⁽²⁰⁾
	Dwivedi AK.	2020	Dwivedi AK. IMMUNITY AND HOMEOPATHY	Homoeopathy, a natural medical approach, boosts the immune system through carefully analyzed medications, considering a patient's physical, mental, and inherited circumstances, resulting in healthier patients and reduced illness. ⁽²¹⁾

VII. DISCUSSION

All selected studies of the pilot study, random control study, systematic review study, anti-miasmatic study in homoeopathy, immunity in homoeopathy, and studies that analyzed the effects of Homoeopathic medicine and were evaluated for treatment for rheumatoid arthritis.

Homoeopathy is based on examining symptoms caused by drugs and applying this knowledge to patients with similar symptoms. There is debate on the exact cause and energy-based behavior of medicine. Observational studies on conventional Chinese, homoeopathy, and Western medicine have shown connections between the Five Elements theory and specific treatments for major organs. The author suggests using traditional Chinese medicine in energy-based treatment, focusing on the cause rather than just symptoms, rather than treating symptoms with homoeopathic drugs. ⁽¹⁹⁾

They are classified as immunosuppressed and non-immunocompetent in an essay written by the author because, as she recently showed, practically all of her patients have an absence of energy in their internal organs. The Constitutional Homeopathy of the Five Elements, based on Traditional Chinese Medicine, uses diluted medicines to improve organ energy... For instance, homeopathic remedies can be used to enhance the immunity of all patients. The author utilizes greatly diluted medications because, by Arndt Shultz's Law, highly concentrated drugs reduce vital energy and are potentially fatal. ⁽²⁰⁾

These signs of a mental illness are not signs of a mental illness. Person's Mental Symptoms A Person's Mental Symptoms are a collection of Changing Symptoms that might help to distinguish the condition.2. Patient Mental Symptoms of patient symptoms are those that can and ought to be altered by a carefully chosen remedy. ⁽²¹⁾

Homoeopathy is a boon for rheumatoid arthritis Bone serves as the framework for the human body and is essential to the body's overall structure. Rheumatoid arthritis is a severe auto-immune condition This condition harms the lining of the joints, leading to damage. Cartilage deteriorates and bulges. The most prevalent rheumatic disease is rheumatoid arthritis, and the use of dubious medications to treat it has been limited. ⁽²²⁾

Using a visual analog scale, patients with rheumatoid arthritis were asked to rate how willing they were to take a medicine linked to 17 particular adverse effects. 35 % of those surveyed said they were unwilling to tolerate the possibility of cosmetic alterations, 38 % of momentary discomfort, and 45% of the potential for substantial toxicity. Patients who had experienced negative outcomes in the past were more accepting of the chance of transient discomfort, significant toxicity, and cosmetic alterations. ⁽²³⁾

Homeopathy provides gentle, permanent cures for conditions like rheumatoid arthritis using potentized medicines. It offers a wide range of treatments without adverse side effects. Further studies are needed for scientific evidence. Homeopathy has good results for providing a permanent cure.

➤ *Rubrics And Their Justifications About Rheumatoid Arthritis*

- *Rubrics:*
It is a clear or brief heading or title that represents a recurrent theme of comparable symptoms listed on their associated drugs in a repertory/ the use of rubrics to translate the patient's symptoms into reportorial language. Examples with some related physical and mental features.

Every symptom contains distinct mental factors generated from people's earlier experiences, resulting in an aggravated sickness. There should always be both physical and mental generals. If the former is sufficiently powerful, the latter may be able to pass for the former.

Table 4 Rubrics and their Justifications about Rheumatoid Arthritis

REMEDY	RUBRICS	SYMPTOMS	INTERPRETATION
BRYONIA [Bry]	[Knerr] [Limbs general] joints: swelling: Rheumatism. in: [complete][Extremities]inflammation Rheumatic joints: [Gentry] [Lower Extremities] Inflammation in Rheumatic inflammation of joints; worse evening and night; intense, bright-red, shining swelling, sensitive to least contact; ⁽²⁴⁾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disturbed, averse to being • Talk indisposed to, desires to be silent, taciturn. ⁽²⁵⁾ 	The unusual symptoms of Bryonia rheumatism get worse with even the smallest movement. Consider that Bryonia's basic feeling is one of loss, which must be swiftly made up for, to further explain this symptom. They will suffer these strange symptoms as a result of their financial loss since he is quiet and dislikes interruptions. Being a tubercular miasm, it frequently causes joint symptoms to change or move. ⁽²⁵⁾
RHUS TOXICODENDRON [Rhus-t]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rubrics: [Knerr] [Limbs in General] joints: Rheumatism: ⁽²⁴⁾ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety, air, in the open, ameliorate • Fear, superstitious. • Fear, poisoned, of being ⁽²⁵⁾ 	Rhus Toxicodendron feels abandoned and powerless by others while also being in There is a risk of being attacked by one's family members.. He can't settle down for any amount of sleep due to his ongoing anxiety. Additionally, this anxiety is more prevalent inside the home, and getting outside helps to reduce it. He is extremely superstitious, as evidenced by his claims that eating sour food causes joint discomfort and that consuming yogurt or Eating curd can lead to stiffness in the neck, which can be mistakenly attributed to superstition or fear of being poisoned. These are evident here. ⁽²⁵⁾
PULSATILLA [Puls]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Phatak] [Phatak A-Z] Arthritis deformans: ⁽²⁴⁾ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Symptoms ever changing; no two chills, no stools no two attacks alike, very well one hour, very miserable the next. • Changing and contradictory symptoms have no head or tail to them. ⁽²⁵⁾ 	Pulsatilla is characterized by a prevailing sense of gentleness. The belief is that one can endure by being gentle and soft, rather than rigid and inflexible. In terms of physical symptoms, Pulsatilla often experiences wandering and fluctuating aches and pains. The sensations that the mind experiences are reflected on the body and they are never fixed. Or permanent. ⁽²⁵⁾
CALCAREA CARBONICA [Calc]	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ascending (breathlessness, weakness). • Exertion of any kind. ⁽²⁵⁾ 	Bone and joint afflictions are frequently a part of Calcarea carbon's pathology. Calcarea's primary emotion is a need for security and stability. Calcium not only strengthens human bones but also forms shells, exoskeletons, etc. for earlier forms of life. The Carbonates' main idea is a crucial reaction. ⁽²⁵⁾
Thuja Occidentalis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Knerr] [Limbs in general] limb: Rheumatism: Arthritis deformans, better morning⁽²⁴⁾ • Delusion, The body is delicate. • Delusion, The body is thin. • Delusion, The body is brittle. • Delusion, that she is made of glass. • insanity, will not be touched. • Sensation as if something above the abdomen, like limbs, were made of glass and would break. • Eruptions only on covered parts. • Sweats on uncovered parts. ⁽²⁶⁾ 	NA	Thuja is a remedy with strong sycotic characteristics. One of its primary symptoms is feeling weak, or fragile. This, in my opinion, is the sycotic perception of having a flaw or being weak within oneself. The dread of being weak in front of others makes up this fragile feeling on an emotional level. Thus, he provides a positive image of himself and worries that any small mistake could disclose the true him—or the negative side of him—that he has worked so hard to hide. The person with When speaking to a doctor, Thuja's personality tends to be secretive and speaks in a hushed tone while remaining aware of others' presence. Stiffness, a physical manifestation of fixity, is one example of this. ⁽²⁵⁾

Table 5 As a Result, Some Significant RA Rubrics are Provided below after Referring to Numerous Repertories

SYMPTOMS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS	KENT REPERTORY ⁽²⁴⁾	REPERTORY OF THE SYMPTOMS OF RHEUMATISM ⁽²⁷⁾	SYNTHESIS REPERTORY ⁽²⁶⁾
Rheumatic Pain in joints of the finger	[Kent] [Extremities Spain] PAIN: Fingers: Joints: Rheumatic:	FINGRS – PAIN Joints –	EXTREMITIES - PAIN - Fingers - Joints - rheumatic
Fever with pain in the joint	[Kent][Extremities pain]PAIN:Tearing:Joints: Fever, during:	GENERAL-FEVER-pain – severe – rheumatic	GENERALS - PAIN - Joints - fever
Pain in small joints	[Kent] [Extremities pain] PAIN: Toes: Joints of Small joints:	GENERAL – ARTRITIS – small joint	GENERALS - PAIN - rheumatic - Joints - Small joints
Stiffness of joints	[Kent][Extremities]STIFFNESS: Joints:	GENERAL-JOINTS-stiffness	EXTREMITIES - STIFFNESS - Joints - rheumatic
Swelling of joints	[Kent][Extremities]SWELLING: Joints:	GENERAL-JOINTS-swelling	GENERALS - SWELLING - Joints; of
Inflammation of joints	[Kent][Extremities]INFLAMMATION: Joints:	GENERAL – INFLAMATORY –pain severe-rheumatism.	GENERALS - INFLAMMATION - Joints; of - rheumatic
Hard nodular lumps present in fingers	NA	FINGERS – ARTHRITIC –nodosities in joints	EXTREMITIES - ARTHRITIC nodosities- Finger joints
Hard nodular lumps present in joints with deformity of joints	NA	GENERAL –ARTHRTIS –nodosa deformans	EXTREMITIES - ARTHRITIS DEFORMANS

Table 6 Here, an Effort is Made to Explain a few of the Autoimmune Rubrics Included in the Synthesis Repertory Mind Chapter⁽²⁶⁾

RUBRICS	INTERPRETATION
Abstraction of mind	A destroying sign that suggests that the mind has lost something
Involuntary	The will and the muscles are totally out of sync. spontaneous or unplanned behaviour
Automatism	Automatic process. Even if something is in the right position, an organized individual will unconsciously arrange things in the right place.
Aversion, herself to	An intense sense of dislike for oneself
Blames himself	To accept responsibility for information or mistakes made
Biting	a person's altered state of consciousness that makes them want to bite objects or articles.
Blindness pretending	a wilful and intentional attempt to represent oneself as blind
Brutality	the state of being extremely brutal, violent, and cold-blooded
Cruelty	Lower than brutality.
Contemptuous oneself of	Lack of admiration of oneself, or a state of putting oneself down
Censorious oneself to	Being very critical of oneself
Delusion	A wrong assumption with inconsistent proof
Destructiveness	A natural person who enjoys inflicting pain on others is cruel and hard-hearted, lacking moral obligation.
Despair	due to illness or other circumstances, loses all hope and confidence
Detached	separation or detachment from emotional, intellectual, or social participation, which is present in depression and schizophrenia
Delusion wrong done	Succeed means achieving desired or expected results, but hardworking individuals often face negative outcomes due to numerous failures in their lives, leading them to believe they will never succeed.
Eccentricity	a deviation from the accepted normative behavior
Ennui, tedium	boredom with life, losing interest in enjoyable pursuits, and common daily activities
Euphoria	A heightened sense of well-being
Exhilaration	Inordinately happy without sufficient cause
Fanaticism	Intolerant of any beliefs or ideas that differ from his own, including those related to politics or religion
fancies	imagination, particularly fantasy-based imagination
Hurting himself	Causing pain or injury to self
Indifference	lack of interest in or concern for family, friends, or the workplace
Injuring himself	Causing physical harm or damage to oneself mentally or physically
Far way	Depression-like apathy and indifference to the future
Forsaken feeling	A feeling of being abandoned
Godless	Lack of reverence for God
Homosexuality	An erotic attraction toward same sex
Hysteria	an emotional neurosis characterized by amnesia, somnambulism, etc.

Imbecility	A feeble-minded person with a defect in mental ability
Remorse	painful recollection of wrongdoing, bitter regrets resulting from repentance for previous conduct
Self-blaming	The patient blames him or her for a stressful event
Torturing	Threatening and tormenting
Tormenting	His minor problem causes great grief, anguish, and distress to others around him.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The majority of the studies analyzed the effects of Homoeopathic medicine and were evaluated for treatment for rheumatoid arthritis. The Google Scholar, a bibliography, pilot study, random control study, a systematic review study, anti-miasmatic study in homoeopathy, immunity in homoeopathy, a Selection of clinical rubrics from Radar 10-Synthesis, homeopath firefly Repertories, Synthesis Repertory Zomeo Elite Homeopathic Software Version 14.0.0 after analysis of abstracts of 17 studies.

The studies were heterogeneous regarding rheumatoid arthritis i.e., Autoimmune disorder. The cause of autoimmune disorders in women is thought to be higher than in males, but according to the homeopathic theory, if there is autoimmunity at the physical level, it can also be preceded by autoimmunity at the mental level. Specifically, in terms of destructiveness, self-destruction, and self-blame by herself/himself. Here, an attempt is made to explain mind rubrics connected to autoimmune by making use of synthetic repertory homeopathic treatment, which can be made simple if autoimmunity at the level of mind is understood. Homeopathic remedies work to encourage the body's mechanisms for healing. Since homeopaths believe that physical sickness frequently has emotional or psychological causes, a homeopathic diagnosis considers the patient's constitution, current emotional and psychological condition, and physical symptoms. More research is necessary for further exploration.

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